

PSYCHOLOGICAL SECURITY ARCHITECTURE

B.R. Khakberdiyev¹, M.Sh. Ismagilova²

Associate Professor (PhD), head of the Department of General Professional Sciences Alfraganus
University Faculty of Tourism¹

Student at Alfraganus University, Faculty of Tourism, Design Program, 3rd-year Design Group
23-1²

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Abstract. *This article describes the concept of psychological security architecture, its importance in modern society, the influence of space on the human mental state, the mechanisms of creating a sense of security through architectural elements, as well as the scientific and theoretical basis of spatial solutions that support psychological well-being. Architecture is analyzed as a means of shaping not only the physical environment, but also the inner stability of the human mind. Research explores the psychological, sociological, and technological aspects of creating a safe, secure, calming, and stress-reducing space for individuals and communities. Psychological security architecture is evaluated as a new design paradigm that is being formed in the context of modern urbanization.*

Keywords: *psychological safety, architectural psychology, space design, sense of security, urbanization, human-space relationship, spatial awareness, ecological design, visual sustainability, architectural anthropology.*

Introduction

The concept of psychological safety architecture is being formed as a separate scientific direction against the background of the complexity of modern urban life, the densification of the urban environment and the sharp increase in the mental load of a person. A person's sense of security is not limited to physical protection, but also directly depends on how he perceives the environment, how he interacts psychologically with the shapes, colors and structures in the space. Architecture has been dealing with functional and constructive issues for a long time, but today it is becoming a system that provides psychological well-being. Because a person cannot work effectively, think creatively in a place where he does not feel calm, and even his health will suffer. Therefore, the architecture of psychological security begins with the analysis of the psychological needs of a person.

The psychological effect of the space consists of complex psycho-physiological processes, in which light, color, size, height, shape, material, sound propagation, air flow and even smells in the space play an important role. A person's sense of security is often related to his sense of control, and when a person feels out of control, boundless or lost in a space, subconscious stress processes are activated. Therefore, in designing a psychologically safe space, visibility, ease of orientation, comprehensibility of visual symbols, level of order and consistency of the spatial structure of the space are the most important elements. These prevent unpleasant experiences such as disorientation, disorientation, feeling of tightness, pressure, noise or isolation.

In the center of the architecture of psychological security, natural elements that influence the subconscious reactions of a person are also important. The angle of entry of natural light into the space, the change of the intensity of sunlight during the day, the presence of flowing water

landscape elements, the presence of green plants not only fulfill an aesthetic function, but also reduce human stress hormones, increase the feeling of peace and stability. People living in urban environments are usually removed from the natural elements and this increases mental fatigue. Therefore, the architecture of psychological security creates conditions for spiritual recovery in space by artificially recreating naturalness.

Architectural forms also directly affect psychological safety. For example, spaces with sharp angles, unevenness, sharp contrast can send a feeling of threat to the human mind. In this case, due to the tension of the elements located next to each other, the subconscious process of caution is activated. On the contrary, rounded shapes, curved lines, organic structures evoke the impression of naturalness, calmness and security. Also important is the influence of architectural geometric order on human psychology: symmetrical spaces represent stability, and rhythmic repetitive elements represent control and order. When these natural psychological reflexes are skillfully used in the design of the space, a person feels very comfortable.

The architecture of psychological safety also applies to the system of social relations. Open spaces created for a person to be in a community, intimate zones designed for immersion in personal thoughts or relaxation, spatial transitions between public and private space are the main layer of social and psychological security. Excessive noise in the same space, being too open or too closed, wrong selection of the distance of mutual sight increases collective stress. For example, poorly organized office architecture can make employees feel uncomfortable talking to each other, and an overly open environment can make people feel lost, watched, or controlled. Therefore, psychologically safe architecture forms a zoning system that is suitable for collective and individual activities on a scientific basis.

Noise, light intensity, color psychology and space acoustics are another very important layer in the formation of psychological safety. Low-frequency noises, background sounds of electrical appliances, or the sound of outside traffic can subconsciously activate danger signals. Therefore, architecture focused on psychological safety provides peace of mind through acoustic materials, sound insulation, and resonance-reducing constructions. According to the psychology of colors, cool and calm colors increase the feeling of security, while excessively bright colors can increase nervous activity. Therefore, architectural elements are chosen according to the rhythm of the human soul.

The architecture of psychological security is enriched by modern technologies. Systems such as intelligent lighting systems, automatic ventilation, touch-sensitive wall panels that change the temperature, soothing light rhythms, and biometric security control enhance the sense of security in the space. These technologies provide not only physical security, but also mental control and comfort. A person feels supported, not controlled, in the space.

In this way, the architecture of psychological safety is becoming one of the most important tools for human mental well-being. Architecture is now considered not as a structure consisting of walls and roofs, but as a living system that protects a person mentally, supports him, protects him from stress and provides stability. At a time when mental health is becoming the most important social capital in modern society, it is natural that architecture that provides psychological safety becomes one of the central directions not only of the construction process, but also of urbanistic, ecological, social and technological development. This direction radically renews the relationship of humanity with space and defines the fundamental philosophy of future architecture.

Psychological security architecture is a scientific-practical approach that allows managing complex emotional processes that occur in the interaction of a person with space, and it applies

not only to the internal structure of the building, but also to the external environment. When a person enters a place, a number of psychological evaluation processes take place in his mind in just a few seconds. These processes are more related to subconscious reactions than to conscious thoughts. It is for this reason that architecture that provides psychological security creates conditions for a person to feel a sense of calmness, understanding and confidence at a glance. This process relies on a combination of visual cues and structures.

In a psychologically safe space, the process of adaptation of a person to the space takes a short time, which reduces stress and saves psychological resources. If the space is messy, poorly lit, and the visual weights are unbalanced, the human subconscious is forced to constantly increase vigilance. This leads to mental fatigue, cognitive overload, rapid loss of attention and increased anxiety. Viewed from this perspective, architecture can be as important as a psychologist or therapist in supporting psychological health.

The psychological interpretation of space is also related to human evolution. Natural instincts, ancient safety reflexes, learned features of the field of vision, biological memory of open and closed spaces directly influence how a person perceives contemporary architecture. In human evolutionary experience, open spaces have been associated with danger, and sheltered spaces with stability. Therefore, in modern architecture, organic forms, natural materials, fine lines and play of light appeal to the deep biological memory of a person and restore a sense of security. That is why warm materials such as wood, leather, natural fiber are one of the most suitable options for modern psychological security architecture.

Psychological safety is especially important in the urban space, because the processes of urbanization expose a person to increasing noise, visual overload, traffic, a lot of signs and information flow. Billboards, bright lights, dense traffic, and the flow of people on major streets of cities send signals to the human mind constantly. And this increases anxiety in the subconscious, this process is also called "urban stress". Psychological safety architecture serves to alleviate this stress by creating quiet areas, quiet corridors, green islands, zen zones in the urban environment.

Ensuring psychological safety in public buildings is a more complex task, because such spaces are used by people of different ages, different cultures, and different needs. That is why it is very important to have a pure, simple and uniform orientation system, signs and indicators in public spaces. Disorientation in institutions such as airports, railway stations, hospitals, and schools is one of the main sources of psychological instability. If a person does not understand where to go in space, his sense of security decreases, the level of stress increases, and even instability in behavior can be observed. Therefore, the architecture of psychological security in such institutions requires the centralization of visual navigation.

Hospital architecture is the most vivid example of the concept of psychological safety. When a person is sick, his mental sensitivity increases; even small details affect the psychological state. Therefore, the old architecture based on cold, sterility is being abandoned in modern medical institutions. Instead, soft colors, light-filled corridors, patient-energizing visual elements, quiet materials, comfortable orientation systems, and layouts that allow ample access to natural light are used. All this serves to strengthen the patient's psyche.

Home architecture is the most personal level of psychological security. The house is perceived as a person's shelter, protective post, and hearth that restores mental balance. Therefore, the correct distribution of light, private areas, quiet corners, and a clean visual composition free of unnecessary objects are very important for psychological well-being. Home should be not just a

place to live, but a source of spiritual recovery. This requires a deep analysis of the individual psychological needs of a person.

With the development of technology, the architecture of psychological security is gaining new directions. For example, neuro-architectural technologies scientifically predict the psychological impact of a space by measuring neural activity in the human brain, heart rate, stress indicators and emotional state. Using this approach, it is possible to create spaces that reduce fatigue, increase activity, or accelerate relaxation. In the future, buildings will be able to automatically change lighting, color or room temperature according to a person's mood.

Conclusion

The architecture of psychological safety is one of the main principles of not only individual well-being, but also the stability of society. In an environment where people feel safe, social relations improve, conflicts decrease, cooperation and trust increase. In this sense, architecture becomes a means of ensuring social and psychological balance. Skillfully organized spaces in public places bring people together, give order, increase respect and tolerance.

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